

Amperometric Determination of As(III) with Potassium Permanganate in Acid Medium Containing Fluoride Ions

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A method is described for the amperometric determination of trivalent arsenic using the rotating Pt. electrode. It depends on the oxidation of As^{3+} to As^{5+} in H_2SO_4 solutions with $KMnO_4$ in presence of fluoride ions under the following conditions : Acidity : 0.1-0.6N H_2SO_4 ; NaF : concentration, 0.4-1.2% (2-6 ml. of 2% solution/10 ml); amount of As^{3+} titrated : 24.2 mg.-8.8 μ g. Reversed L-shaped curves were obtained and the results agreed with those of potentiometric titrations.

TRIVALENT arsenic was determined amperometrically in various supporting electrolytes by the direct iodide method¹, and by titration with $KBrO_3$ or Iodine³. Chloramine T⁴ was also used as titrant for amperometric determination of As(III). Bambach⁵ developed a procedure for determining arsenic in biological material. As(III) was determined in commercial phosphoric acid⁶. The reaction between trivalent arsenic and potassium permanganate in sulphuric acid medium containing fluoride ions was recently studied both visually and potentiometrically by Issa and Hamdy⁷. However, literature is difficult for a study involving amperometric determination of As(III) with $KMnO_4$ in fluoride media. It is well known that permanganate is reduced at zero applied e.m.f. It is aimed in the present investigation to study the reaction between As(III) and $KMnO_4$ amperometrically using the rotating platinum electrode vs saturated calomel electrode as reference in order to elucidate the conditions of which a quantitative determination of As(III) could be carried out.

Experimental

Solutions :

The potassium permanganate solutions were prepared by a method similar to that of Stamm⁸ and standardised with sodium oxalate⁹. Sodium arsenite solutions were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of A.R. sodium arsenite in twice distilled water and standardised by the bromate method¹⁰. Dilute solutions of sodium arsenite and potassium permanganate were prepared by quantitative successive dilution with bidistilled water. Other solutions including 2% NaF, $\sim 2N H_2SO_4$ were prepared from the C.P. products in twice distilled water.

Equipment and Procedure :

The apparatus used is shown in Fig. 1, the attainment of a steady diffusion current was maintained

by rotating the pt electrode at a constant speed of 600 r.p.m. A S.C.E. was used as reference electrode. The arsenite solution was mixed with the appropriate

Fig. 1.

amount of NaF and sulphuric acid, completed to known volume with bidistilled water (usually 10 ml), and titrated with $KMnO_4$. The diffusion current corrected for dilution was calculated and plotted against the volume of permanganate. The dilution correction is made by multiplying the current mea-

sured by a factor of $\frac{V+v}{v}$, where V is the original volume and v is the volume of titrant added. The titration curves are approximately reversed L-shaped as shown in Figs. 2-4.

Results and Discussion

It is well-known that permanganate is reduced at zero applied e.m.f. and therefore no applied voltage

is required. However, the amperometric titration using rotating platinum electrode is of practical importance because of its simplicity and rapidity. The equivalence point can be determined from a few

Fig. 2. Titration of 2 ml 0.043N NaAsO₂ with 0.0184N KMnO₄ in presence of 5 ml 2% NaF (Total volume ~10 ml).

(A) 0.04N H₂SO₄, (B) 0.1N H₂SO₄, (C) 0.2N H₂SO₄, (D) 0.4N H₂SO₄, (E) 0.6N H₂SO₄, (F) 0.8N H₂SO₄, (G) 1.2N H₂SO₄.

readings on each side of the end point. Moreover, it is not necessary to titrate slowly near the end point, whereas in potentiometric titrations the equilibrium becomes sluggish as the concentrations of the reactants decrease⁷. The conditions liable to affect

Fig. 3. Titration of 2 ml 0.043N NaAsO₂ with 0.0184N KMnO₄ in presence of 0.4N H₂SO₄ (Total volume ~10 ml).

A—0.5 of 2% NaF, B—1 ml of 2% NaF,
C—2 ml of 2% NaF, D—6 ml of 2% NaF,
E—8 ml of 2% NaF.

quantitative determination of As(III) include acidity, sodium fluoride concentration, and the concentration of trivalent arsenic. In what follows these factors are varied in order to elucidate the proper conditions under which the oxidation of As(III) with KMnO₄ proceeds smoothly in accordance with the following equation:

As is obvious from Figs. 2–4 the titration curves are approximately reversed L-shaped. The current increases slowly as the permanganate solution is added during the titration. When all the arsenite has been oxidised, the current increases rapidly owing to the reduction of the permanganate added along the other branch of the reversed L-shaped curve. The intersect of the two branches gives the end point.

Effect of acidity:

The results recorded in Table 1 and the curves shown in Fig. 1, represent the effect of acidity on the accuracy of the end point on titrating 2 ml. of 0.043N As(III) with 0.023N KMnO₄ (normality of

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ACIDITY

Titration of 2 ml 0.043N NaAsO₂ with 0.0184N KMnO₄ in presence of 5 ml 2% NaF and different acidities (Total volume 10 ml).

No.	Acidity N H ₂ SO ₄	Vol. of KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theore- tical end point (ml)	Error (%; ±)	Remarks
a	0.04	4.73	4.67	1.28	turbid
b	0.1	4.70	4.67	0.64	brown.
c	0.2	4.70	4.67	0.64	
d	0.4	4.67	4.67	nil	
e	0.6	4.68	4.67	0.21	
f	0.8	4.53	4.67	3.03	
g	1.2	4.55	4.67	2.60	

permanganate based on valency change 7 to 2 and hence must be multiplied by 0.8) in presence of 5 ml 2% NaF using a total volume of 10 ml. These data show that good results are obtained at acidities ranging from 0.1 to 0.6N H₂SO₄. At lower acidities

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SODIUM FLUORIDE

Titration of 2 ml 0.043N NaAsO₂ with 0.0184N KMnO₄ in 0.4N H₂SO₄ and different volumes of 2% NaF (Total volume 10 ml).

No.	Vol. of 2% NaF (ml)	Vol. of KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theore- tical end point (ml)	Error (%; ±)	Remarks
a	0.5	4.48	4.67	4.07	Solution
b	1	4.60	4.67	1.49	turbid
c	2	4.67	4.67	nil	brown.
d	6	4.67	4.67	nil	
e	8	4.63	4.67	0.85	

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF ARSENITE(III) CONCENTRATION

Titration of different concentrations of NaAsO₂ with KMnO₄ in 0.4N H₂SO₄ and 5 ml 2% NaF

No.	Vol. of As ³⁺ (ml)	Normality of As ³⁺ (N)	Amount of As ³⁺ (mg)	Vol. of N KMnO ₄ consumed (ml)	Theor. end point (ml)	Error (%; ±)	Total Vol. (ml)	
a	0.5	4.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.00881	0.52 ml	4.48 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.52	ml	10
b	2	4.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0353	2.11 ml	4.48 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.10	0.48	10
c	5	4.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.088	5.25 ml	4.48 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.25	ml	10
d	2	8.8 × 10 ⁻³	0.66	3.99 ml	4.48 × 10 ⁻³	3.91	0.26	10
e	2	4.3 × 10 ⁻²	3.225	4.66 ml	0.0184	4.67	0.21	10
f	6	4.3 × 10 ⁻²	9.678	3.48 ml	0.0748	3.49	0.29	10
g	10	4.3 × 10 ⁻²	16.125	5.83 ml	0.0748	5.82	0.17	20
h	15	4.3 × 10 ⁻²	24.195	8.70 ml	0.0748	8.72	0.23	25

the solution gets turbid brown as a result of precipitation of MnO₂ and the titration yields erroneous results. Similarly, when the acidity is raised above 0.6N H₂SO₄, the end points are attained earlier than expected due to the partial reduction of permanganate to bivalent manganese.

Effect of sodium fluoride concentration :

The data representing the effect of F⁻ ions concentration are shown in Table 2 and represented graphically in Fig. 2. It is obvious that end points

Fig. 4. Titration of As³⁺ with KMnO₄ in presence of 0.4N H₂SO₄ and 5 ml of 2% NaF.

- A—0.5 ml 4.7 × 10⁻⁴N As³⁺ + 4.48 × 10⁻⁴N KMnO₄
- B— 5 ml 4.7 × 10⁻⁴N As³⁺ + 4.48 × 10⁻⁴N KMnO₄
- C— 2 ml 8.8 × 10⁻³N As³⁺ + 4.48 × 10⁻³N KMnO₄
- D— 2 ml 4.3 × 10⁻²N As³⁺ + 1.84 × 10⁻²N KMnO₄
- E—10 ml 4.3 × 10⁻²N As³⁺ + 7.48 × 10⁻²N KMnO₄
- F—15 ml 4.3 × 10⁻²N As³⁺ + 7.48 × 10⁻²N KMnO₄

coinciding fairly well with the theoretical values are obtained on using 0.4–1.2% NaF (corresponding to 2–6 ml of the 2% NaF). The solution becomes

turbid brown when 1 ml of the sodium fluoride solution is used due to production of MnO₂ which renders the reaction very sluggish.

Effect of Arsenite concentration :

The amperometric titration of varying amounts of arsenite with KMnO₄ is carried out under the proper conditions of acidity and NaF concentration. The results obtained are shown in Table 4 and Fig. 4. The titration curves are nearly always reversed L-shaped curves. The data indicate that amounts of As(III) varying from 8.8 mg to 24.2 mg could be determined by the amperometric method with an error not exceeding 0.5%.

The reaction between arsenite and potassium permanganate in acid medium containing fluoride ions was studied potentiometrically⁷. The amperometric titration of arsenite using rotating pt electrode has the advantage of rapidity and simplicity over the potentiometric method. Also, the use of the rotating pt electrode is practically simple and more useful than the D.M.E. Since permanganate is reduced at zero e.m.f. it is not necessary to apply an external e.m.f. The method reveals the feasibility of determining As(III) in amounts ranging from 24.2 mg to 8.8 μg with fair accuracy. This appears to be of some importance in determining As(III) in biological material e.g., in case of arsenic poisoning.

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